

Regarding the Psychological Criteria and Factors of Origin of Conflicts between Young People

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Abstract:

In this article, the conflicts that arise during adolescence, the factors of their occurrence, the interests, needs, views, etc. between the parties in interpersonal relations. Problems such as the origin of conflicts and the emergence of conflicts based on these conflicts, as well as social empowerment and social empowerment are highlighted.

Keywords: Adolescence, conflicts, interests, needs, social reinforcement, social reinforcement, conflict group integration.

The most difficult stage of childhood is adolescence. During this period, the child experiences a transitional stage, that is, the transition from childhood to adulthood. We will reflect on this period and its specific aspects. Adolescence is a unique period of a person's life, in which psychological conditions such as the rapid development of secondary sexual organs, changes in body structure, the formation of self-perceptions, and an increase in maximalism in relation to the external environment are observed.

Another characteristic characteristic of adolescence is the observation of conflict situations. Adolescent conflicts are very different from conflicts at other times. We will try to study the psychological characteristics of the observed conflicts between them, which are typical until the period of adolescence. It is one of the urgent issues of our time to research this uniqueness, to study the conflicts observed in teenagers based on these situations. When defining conflicts, we pay special attention to their conflicting aspects, that is, the interests, needs, views, etc. between the parties. causes contradictions, and conflicts arise based on these contradictions. However, at this point, the question of exactly what kind of opposition can be called a conflict is relevant. And this naturally goes back to the issue of their psychological criteria. We will address these criteria below.

According to a group of scientists, it is necessary to pay attention to the following situations when solving this problem (2,3,4):

- 1) interdependence of the parties, that is, both parties are interdependent, the activity of one person ensures the actions of the second person, and these actions call for the response reactions of the first subject, and in this way, the interaction of the parties occurs, their control is observed, but if there are strict rules of communication (for example, a boxer's fight), this is not a conflict;
- 2) awareness of the conflict of the situation, that is, one side or both sides evaluate the actions of others as hostile actions aimed at destroying the achievement of desired goals or fighting;
- 3) choosing the strategy of the second behavior: seeking compromise or a solution that is acceptable to both parties, or escalating the conflict, intensifying the struggle, for example, moving from the struggle of points of view (cognitive conflict) to the struggle of individuals (interpersonal conflict), then to the struggle of groups and reaping excellence.

There are no guilty parties or rights in the conflict, everyone wants to achieve their goals. Conflict is a type of interaction in which the outcome affects all participants in the conflict, each person contributes to the conflict. However, usually a person thinks: "The conflict is not mine, the other person is to blame", "I am right, and the other person is wrong, he is bad", and each person gathers allies around him to prove his right. This is how the conflict escalates. The outcome of the conflict is not always the same. The dispute will end by itself in the case of agreement between the parties or in the case of one of the parties withdrawing from the conflict, as well as in the case of reconciliation due to the intervention of third parties. As noted above, conflict is an exaggerated form of contradictions, but at the same time, it serves as a way of identifying and resolving contradictions. In this sense, the question arises: what causes the conflict, what are the stages of its development? It can be answered as follows: the conflict is caused by an objective life situation created by the opposite parties, and these parties themselves have certain interests, needs, and goals. Naturally, the non-recognition of some needs of one side by the other forms the socio-psychological basis of the conflict. This itself is a structure of contradictions, and it creates a conflict situation that has not turned into a conflict. Thus, a conflict situation is such a complex of human needs and interests that creates the ground for a real struggle between different social subjects. The subject of the dispute is such a fundamental contradiction that the parties enter into a struggle for this reason and to resolve this contradiction.

During the conflict, as the disagreement is resolved, a way out of the impasse is sought, and then the question of the function of the conflict is raised - positive or negative, good or bad. In other words, is conflict good or bad? Here, from our usual point of view, we give a causal answer, because the conflict always takes the form of family quarrels and disagreements, service anxieties, inter-ethnic, territorial, socio-political antagonisms, sufferings and losses. Based on this, it has become a habit to look at the conflict as a negative event. However, if you look closely at the essence of this problem, you will see a different perspective, a different ageism. Based on this, the conflict can be considered not only a negative social phenomenon, but also a positive one. Our opinion here is as follows: indeed, conflict is an unpleasant, unwanted phenomenon that begins to erode a normally functioning social system, but in the course of the conflict, such forces appear that can restore peace and tranquility to the system, as well as keep it in a stable state. Along with this, there is also a view of the conflict as a deviation from the norm, contrary to the mood of viewing it as a norm of social relations, a normal state of society.

Carrying out a motivational analysis of controversial behavior, P. I. Ilin emphasizes that a conflict is such an interaction between two parties that the realization of the goals of one party contradicts the goals of the other party, that is, competition appears as an objective situation, and on the other hand, emotional-emotional dislike of the other person, the mood of competitive interaction between

people, their various psychological characteristics cause conflicting behavior. While conflicts are inevitable in human interaction, they can also serve a positive constructive function:

- the conflict, denying stagnation, gives impetus to a certain movement towards the past;
- in the course of the conflict, the object of the source of disagreement occurs and it becomes possible to resolve it, to "remove" it, to find means to prevent future conflicts;
- Conflict is a way of self-affirmation, especially in teenagers, a form of behavior necessary to maintain status in a conflict group.
- conflict within the group in scientific activity creates the level of tension necessary for creative activity; therefore, the research showed that the productivity of creative scientific activity is higher in conflicted individuals;
- Intergroup conflicts contribute to group integration, stability, resolution of conflict situations, attracting attention, blurring of group members to the common life of the group.

In studying the problem of conflicts and their nature, determining their causes is considered an important point. The analysis of social and socio-psychological research allows to distinguish the following main causes of conflicts:

- determines the emergence and emergence of existing socio-economic relations in the socio-economic society of today;
- socio-psychological needs, motives and goals of the activities and behaviors of various people;
- Differences in behavioral motives and goals in social demographics of people. These differences appear depending on people's gender, age, and ethnicity.

As people pay attention to changing socio-economic situations, they do so based on their interests and needs. Naturally, giving attention to some of these needs and denying some of them causes social reasons for conflicts. The disparity in the level of income and purchases between the richest and the poorest, the virtual absence of the middle layers of society, the instability of social, economic and political development inevitably causes conflicts at different levels: between individuals, at the level of the whole society. The instability of society and the level of conflict arise from various factors: a high emotional psychological state against the background of interaction between people, an increase in dissatisfaction with the economic situation and life, an increase in vocal conflict, the transformation of deviant behavior into specific social "norms" (quarrels, racketeering, terrorism, drug addiction, prostitution, etc.), "looking for the culprit" (what should be done and who is to blame?). On the other hand, similar negative psychological factors do not have a good effect on the development of the social, economic and political situation.

Social empowerment is characterized by the following parameters:

- a) Spread of dissatisfaction with life (price increase, inflation, impoverishment of the shopping basket, fear of personal safety, etc.)
- b) loss of confidence in the ruling elite (pessimism in the assessment of the future, increased sense of risk, emergence of an atmosphere of public mental unrest and emotional agitation);
- c) Emergence of spontaneous mass movements (various conflicts, rallies, demonstrations, strikes).

The main stages of social empowerment are:

- 1) the background level of social intensity is the norm:
- 2) the hidden stage of the growth of social conflict - its balancing above the norm or within its limits;

- 3) the stage of social empowerment, the increase of dissatisfaction and the realization that the situation that has arisen is a conflict;
 - 4) the critical stage of the transition of social protest to a sharp conflict;
 - 5) stage of accelerated development of social conflicts - explosion;
 - 6) the highest development stage of social protest - the culmination of the dispute;
 - 7) Such as the stage of social discontent falling to the background level and the end of social conflict.
- Above we touched on the psychological criteria of conflicts, albeit partially. Well, in today's process of globalization, the question arises as to the origin of conflicts between teenagers and how the problems of their elimination are being solved. First of all, it is characteristic to find a solution to the issues of prevention before conflicts arise. During our research, we came to the conclusion that the factors that cause conflicts among young people are characterized as follows:
 - changes in culture, art and literature, socio-economic conditions as a result of the development of science and technology;
 - due to the expansion of mass media, the level of consciousness of adolescents has increased;
 - sufficient awareness of teenagers about world events, laws of nature and society, history;
 - acceleration of their physical and mental maturity;
 - the problems of transparency, social justice, and democracy are deeply penetrating social life;
 - That adolescents have ample opportunities for independent learning, creative thinking, self-management, understanding, evaluation and control.

The above situations directly affect the psychology of teenagers and have a specific effect on the specifics of conflicts observed in them. It is one of the urgent issues of our time to research this uniqueness, to study the conflicts observed in teenagers based on these situations.

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